

Amino Acid Composition of Fruits and Seeds of Medicinal Plants

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Amino acid profile of some fruits and seeds of indigenous medicinal plants was investigated. The paper chromatograms of the extracts revealed that asparagine and tyrosine in fruit edible parts; alanine, threonine, tyrosine and valine in seeds; and alanine and valine in proteins, were the most widely distributed amino acids. Fruits of *Ficus religiosa*, *F. lacor*, *Litchi chinensis*, and *Morus laevigata*, seeds of *Achras zapota*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Daucus carota*, and *Delonix regia*, and proteins of *Aegle marmelos* and *Ficus bengalensis* are the richest source of amino acids.

VARIOUS aspects of the problems related to the free amino acids have been reported^{1,2}. At present about 500 amino acids are known, of which ca 240 occur free in nature³. Still further, naturally occurring amino acids are being found each year. Some of the unbound amino acids are the essential intermediates in the biosynthesis of particular protein amino acids⁴⁻⁶, while others like γ -methyleneglutamine⁷ and canavanine⁸ are important agents in nitrogen transport and nitrogen storage, respectively. Amino acids act as precursors of many complex molecules in the living cells. Amino acids and proteins are important constituents of our diet. The evaluation of free and bound amino acids of some fruits and seeds have been carried out to determine their nature in the present communication.

Experimental

The fruits and seeds were collected locally. Whatman chromatographic paper no. 42(55×45 cm) was used for quantitative separation of amino acids in descending manner. The solvent systems n-butanol—glacial acetic acid—water (4:1:1, v/v) and phenol—water (3:1, w/w) were used to develop the chromatograms. Tlc (coated with silica gel G), electrophoresis, and circular chromatography techniques were also used in the same solvent systems to detect the amino acids. Two-dimensional chromatography on paper as well as on tlc did not give satisfactory results. The coloured spots were developed on spraying with ninhydrin and heating at 100° for 10 min. The spots were compared with authentic samples of amino acids. Some other spray reagents were also used for the detection of amino acids^{9,10}.

Preparation of extracts of fruits : To each fresh fruits (100 g) distilled water (~250 ml) was added,

the pulp blended for 10 min and then centrifuged. The supernatant liquid was separated, the residue washed with distilled water (3×50 ml) and separated by centrifugation again. The combined supernatant was concentrated by rotatory film evaporator and then used for the evaluation of of unbound amino acids.

Separation of proteins : To each fruit extracts (20 ml) ethanol (95 %) was added until the precipitation was complete. The flocculent precipitates changed to the curdy colour when centrifuged. The supernatant liquid was separated and discarded. The residues were washed with ethanol until the washings revealed negative to ninhydrin test. The purified precipitates were dried over P₂O₅.

Preparation of extracts of seeds : The seeds were powdered in a hand grinder and defatted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). The deoiled seeds were successfully extracted with water, sodium chloride (5%, w/v), ethanol (75%, v/v) and sodium hydroxide (0.25%, w/v) until the extracts were negative to the Biuret test. pH of the extracts were adjusted to precipitate proteins and then separated by centrifugation. The supernatant was concentrated and employed for chromatographic separation of free amino acids in seeds.

Preparation of protein hydrolysates : The purified proteins (20–0 mg) were hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml) containing formic acid (1 ml) for 2 h. The acid hydrolysates, negative to the Biuret test, were repeatedly distilled in vacuum until free from acid to pH 4 to 5 and subjected to chromatographic analysis. Tryptophan was identified in the protein hydrolysates prepared by refluxing the proteins (50 mg) with 5N sodium hydroxide (2 mg) for 6–8 h.

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Results and Discussion

Free amino acid composition of fruits : A comparative study of the chromatograms of fruit extracts indicates that asparagine and tyrosine are most abundant in free state. The other amino acids determined in most of the fruits were alanine, aspartic acid, glycine and threonine. The essential amino acids arginine and methionine were present only in *Aegle marmelos* pulp. Similarly, citrulline and hydroxyproline were only present in fruits of *Achras zapota* and *Morus laevigata*, respectively. Norleucine and norvaline were only determined in the fruits of *Ficus religiosa*. Fruits of *Azadirachta indica*, *Ficus lacor*, *F. religiosa*, *Litchi chinensis* and *Morus laevigata* contained the highest amounts of free amino acids. *Prunus persica* fruit contained only asparagine and proline in free state. Amino acids like tryptophan, β -phenylalanine, ornithine and 3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine could not be detected in any edible part of fruits under investigation. Fruit pulp as well as pericarp of *A. marmelos* contained almost the same concentration of the amino acids. The fruits of *A. zapota*, *P. persica* and *Ficus racemosa* were deficient in essential amino acids.

Free amino acid composition of seeds : The pattern of distribution of free amino acids in seeds was quite different from that observed in fruits. Alanine, threonine, tyrosine and valine were the widely distributed unbound amino acids among seeds. The highest concentration of the amino acids was determined in seeds of *Achras zapota*, *A. indica*, *Daucus carota* and *Delonix regia*, while the seeds of *A. marmelos* and *Cassia fistula* contained the lowest amounts of these compounds. It is interesting to note that the concentration of the amino acids in the seeds of *A. marmelos* being almost the same as detected in its pulp and fruit pericarp. However, the level of the amino acids in the seeds of *P. persica* was higher than observed in its edible part. Investigation on the pericarp of seeds of *P. persica* was also carried out and it was found that only arginine, threonine and γ -aminobutyric acid were present along with one unidentified violet spot on the paper chromatogram. Aspartic acid, isoleucine and lysine were only detected in seed extracts of *A. indica*, *A. marmelos* and *A. zapota*, respectively. The distribution of essential amino acids, arginine, histidine, leucine, methionine and phenylalanine was rare. The presence of glutamine, hydroxyproline and 3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine could not be detected in any seed extract. Gray and Fowden¹¹ reported the presence of α -(methylenecyclopropyl) glycine in seeds of subtropical species of *Litchi chinensis*, which possessed hypoglycemic activity against mice. We could not get any change in colour of the extract of these seeds after treatment with ninhydrin at high temperature. No. coloured

spots were also developed on paper chromatogram and tlc plate. Seeds of *D. regia*, *A. zapota* and *D. carota* were rich in essential amino acids. Sung and Fowden¹² reported the occurrence of *trans*-3-hydroxy-L-proline in an unbound form as a major component of the free amino acid pool of seeds of *D. regia*. In our experiment this compound could not be detected in any seed extract. We also could not succeed to detect the presence of γ -methylene-L-glutamic acid and its corresponding amide, γ -methylene-L-glutamine in *D. regia* seeds as reported by these workers¹².

Amino acid composition of fruit proteins : Alanine and valine were the most widely distributed amino acids in various fruit proteins. Tyrosine, which was determined in free state in most of the fruit and seed extracts, was detected only in the protein hydrolysates of *A. marmelos* pericarp and *F. lacor* fruit. Norleucine and threonine were only observed in the protein of *A. marmelos* pulp. Similarly, serine was only present in the hydrolysate of *F. religiosa* fruit protein. Some amino acids were determined only in the protein hydrolysates of two species only, e.g. arginine in *L. chinensis* and *P. persica*; cysteine in *Ficus bengalensis* and *F. religiosa*; phenylalanine in *F. religiosa* and *L. chinensis*; and proline in *A. marmelos* pericarp and *P. persica*. The essential amino acids like histidine in *A. marmelos*, *F. bengalensis* and *F. racemosa*; isoleucine in *F. racemosa*, *F. religiosa* and *L. chinensis*; leucine in *A. zapota*, *F. bengalensis* and *F. lacor*; and lysine in *A. marmelos* pericarp, *F. bengalensis* and *F. lacor* were found to be rare. Some amino acids like glutamine, methionine and tryptophan could not be detected in any protein hydrolysate. The lowest number of amino acids were detected in *P. persica* fruit protein, while *A. marmelos* pericarp and *F. bengalensis* proteins the highest levels of bound amino acids.

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